

Kinetics of Oxidation of Glycollic Acid by Quinquevalent Vanadium in Sulphuric Acid Medium

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The oxidation of glycollic acid by V(V) has been found to be first order both in [oxidant] and [substrate] and second order in $[H^+]$. The acid dependence of oxidation can be expressed by equation $\log k = 1.2 \log [H_2SO_4] - 3.74$. The increase in oxidation rate with increase in $[HSO_4^-]$ at constant $[H^+]$ has also been observed. The thermodynamic parameters have been evaluated. $V(OH)_2^{3+}$ and $V(OH)_2(HSO_4)^{2+}$ have been proposed to be the reactive species out of which the latter one is more reactive. A plausible mechanism with V(V) acting as one electron oxidant involving C-C bond fission in the slow step via free radical formation, has been suggested.

BAKORE and Shanker¹ suggested that in the reaction of glycollic acid with vanadium(V) in perchloric acid medium, vanadium(V) acts as a two electron oxidant involving C-H bond rupture in the slow step. No attempt has been made to study the oxidation of glycollic acid by vanadium(V) in sulphuric acid medium. It was, therefore, thought desirable to undertake a study of oxidation of glycollic acid by vanadium(V) in sulphuric acid medium. The results are reported in this paper.

Experimental

Ammonium metavanadate (Reidel) was dissolved in appropriate concentration of sulphuric acid (B. D. H., AnalaR), to prepare vanadium(V) solution. Other chemicals used were of B. D. H., AnalaR grade. The solutions were standardised by conventional methods.

The solutions of the substrate and the oxidant were equilibrated at desired temperature (± 0.05) before being mixed. Oxidation reactions were followed by quenching aliquotes, withdrawn at regular known intervals of time, in excess of ferrous ammonium sulphate solution and back titrating by standard potassium dichromate solution using N-phenyl anthranilic acid as indicator.

Results and Discussion

The kinetic studies were made by taking glycollic acid and sulphuric acid in sufficient excess over vanadium(V) concentration. The rate of disappearance of V(V) was observed to follow the first order kinetics uniformly. The integrated form of first order rate equation was also used to evaluate the pseudo first order rate constants (k).

The plot of $\log k$ vs $\log [S]_0$ gives a straight line with a positive slope of unity indicating that the order with respect to substrate is also one (Table 1).

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARYING [SUBSTRATE] ON THE RATE OF REACTION

[Vanadium(V)] = 0.005 M; [Glycollic acid] (10^{-2} M)	$[H_2SO_4] = 2$ M; 10^{-4} K (sec^{-1})	temp. = 40° 10^{-2} K ₀
2.00	6.41	32.04
1.42	4.14	29.20
1.25	3.74	29.90
1.11	3.34	30.07
1.00	3.06	30.60

$$k_0 = k/[Substrate]$$

The plot of $1/k$ vs $1/[S]_0$ gives a straight line passing through the origin. This may be taken as a kinetic evidence of the fact that no intermediate compound was formed between vanadium(V) and glycollic acid.

Effect of $[H_2SO_4]$ on the reaction rate: The rate of reaction was found to increase on increasing $[H_2SO_4]$. At 5 M and above, the reaction was practically instantaneous. The plot of $\log k$ vs $\log [H_2SO_4]$ was linear with an intercept obeying Eq. (1).

$$\log k = 1.2 \log [H_2SO_4] - 3.74 \quad \dots (1)$$

Effect of $[H^+]$ on the reaction rate: At constant ionic strength and constant [bisulphate], the plot of k vs $[H^+]^2$ was found to be linear passing through the origin (Fig. 1). As no positive intercept was obtained, it may be supposed that the reaction involves only one path with a rate directly proportional to $[H^+]^2$ and the order with respect to $[H^+]$ was found to be two.

Fig. 1. Plot of k vs $[HSO_4^-]$ at $\mu = 4$ and plot of k vs $[H^+]^2$ at $\mu = 6$;
 [Glycollic acid] = 0.0125 M ; [Vanadium(V)] = 0.005 M and temp = 40°.

Effect of $[HSO_4^-]$ on the reaction rate : The plot of k vs $[HSO_4^-]$ was found to be linear with a positive intercept (Fig. 1). This suggests no direct dependence of rate on $[HSO_4^-]$.

Reactive species of V(V) : The parent reactive species of V(V) in mineral acid is supposed to be present as VO_2^+ which is converted into different forms depending on $[H_2SO_4]$ according to equilibria (2-5).

The linear dependence of the rate on $[H^+]^2$ rules out equilibria (2) and (3), and leads us to conclude that $V(OH)_2^+$ is the real active oxidising species of V(V) and there is no hydrogen ion independent path involving VO_2^+ , as the plot of k vs $[H^+]^2$ passes through the origin. The increase in rate with increase in $[HSO_4^-]$, evident from the linear plot of k vs $[HSO_4^-]$ having a positive intercept, suggests that the species $V(OH)_2(HSO_4)^+$ are better oxidant than $V(OH)_2^+$.

Effect of $[NaClO_4]$ and $[MnSO_4]$ on the reaction rate : No appreciable change in the rate (Table 2) was obtained on increasing $[NaClO_4]$ which indicates that for all practical purposes change in ionic strength had no effect. This naturally suggests

participation of the substrate as a neutral molecule² because oxidant is ionic in nature. Increase in $[MnSO_4]$ has a tendency to accelerate the rate of reaction (Table 2). This effect cannot be due to change in the ionic strength of the medium. Mn(IV) has been found to be a good oxidant for the glycollic acid oxidation³. It is likely that Mn(IV) obtained from the oxidation of Mn(II) by V(V) is responsible for accelerating the rate of reaction.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARYING $[NaClO_4]$ AND $[MnSO_4]$ ON THE REACTION RATE

[Glycollic acid] = 0.0125 M ; [Vanadium(V)] = 0.005 M ; temp. = 40°							
$[NaClO_4]$ (M)	—	0.05	0.10	0.50	—	—	—
$[MnSO_4]$ (M)	—	—	—	—	0.025	0.050	0.075
$10^{-4}k$ (sec ⁻¹)	3.74	3.95	3.88	3.61	3.80	4.02	4.09

Stoichiometry : The stoichiometry of the reaction was studied potentiometrically. Below 3.5 M H_2SO_4 acid medium the stoichiometry was calculated to be four moles of vanadium(V) for one mole of glycollic acid. The final product was found to be formic acid which was identified by chromotropic acid tests⁴. The overall equation can be given by Eq. (6).

Above 3.75 M H_2SO_4 medium the overall reaction was found to satisfy the Eq. (7).

The absence of formaldehyde or formic acid was confirmed by chromotropic acid tests. Only one inflexion, both in direct (substrate in the cell) and reverse (oxidant in the cell) potentiometric titrations, was obtained corresponding to the above-mentioned stoichiometries in both the acid ranges used. This leads us to conclude that the expected intermediate oxidation products get oxidised to the final stage in a fast process.

Influence of temperature : Parallel Arrhenius plots were obtained for both the acid ranges used, suggesting the same rate determining steps in either acid range. From Arrhenius plot, the energy of activation, frequency factor and entropy of activation were calculated and found to be 13.68 Kcal mol⁻¹, 10.77×10^7 and -21.84 e. u. respectively.

Mechanism : On the basis of various experimental observations described, it is now possible to suggest a mechanism of oxidation of glycollic acid by V(V) in sulphuric acid medium. V(V) like Cr(VI) can act both as one or two electron oxidant⁵. In the present case it acts as one electron oxidant because the reaction involves free radical intermediate as is evident from acrylonitrile test. Similar observations have been made by Water and Littler during their studies on V(V) oxidation of alcohols,

ketones and other substrates⁶. The reactive species of V(V) namely $V(OH)_2^{3+}$ and $V(OH)_3(HSO_4)^{2+}$ react with glycollic acid to give free radicals in a slow rate-determining step accompanied by C-C bond fission as it has been suggested by Jones *et al*⁷ in the case of oxidation of other α -hydroxy acids by V(V).

In general the reaction can be written as given below :

The free radical so formed is readily oxidised to formaldehyde

Further oxidation of HCHO into formic acid and finally to carbon dioxide, depending on acid concentration, also takes place through fast steps. Thus the rate equation (10) may be derived.

$$-\frac{d[V(V)]}{dt} = k_1[S][V(V)] \dots (10)$$

Considering both the active species of V(V) the rate equation may be represented by Eq. (11).

$$-\frac{d[V(V)]}{dt} = K_s k_1 [S][VO_2^+][H^+]^2 \{1 + K_4[HSO_4^-]\} \dots (11)$$

If bisulphate complex of V(V) is not considered, Eq. (11) is reduced to the following form :

$$-\frac{d[V(V)]}{dt} = K_s k_1 [S][VO_2^+][H^+]^2 \dots (12)$$

The rate equation so derived is well in conformity with the experimental findings.

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